

THE IMPACT OF UZBEKISTAN'S WTO MEMBERSHIP ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation. This research will give a succinct synopsis of the present economic situation in Uzbekistan, emphasizing both its advantages and disadvantages. By doing this, the framework for comprehending the possible effects of WTO membership will be established. The research will next examine the main points of contention about Uzbekistan's economic gains from WTO membership. Among the main topics that will be examined are improved foreign direct investment, expanded market access for Uzbek exports, and the drive for internal economic reforms. The research will not, however, downplay the possible difficulties that come with being a member of the WTO. We'll take a close look at the possibility of job losses in some industries as a result of growing import competition and the requirement for major changes to domestic policy.

Keywords. GDP per capita, Export, World Trade Organization (WTO), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI).

It seeks to offer a thorough examination of the potential effects that WTO membership may have on Uzbekistan's economic growth. Uzbekistan's membership in the World Trade Organization is important for the economic development of our country and leads to the strengthening of trade integration with the countries of the world. WTO membership expands export opportunities for Uzbekistan and increases the flow of foreign investment to the country. As a result, the sustainable economic growth of the country will accelerate and strengthen its position in the world market

Uzbekistan was one of the earliest applicants from the FSU to join the World Trade Organization. Uzbekistan's admission, however, stalled after four rounds of consultation with WTO working groups in 2005. Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan are the only nations in Central Asia that are not part of the WTO at the present time.

Figure II-3: Central Asian countries' accession status to the WTO.

source: wto.org, compiled by the author.

Recent OECD, WTO, and World Bank Group analyses indicate that "gains from GVC participation are not immediate." "The benefits of GVC participation differ depending on whether a country operates at the top or bottom of the value chain." Consequently, the costs and dangers of participation in GVCs might vary considerably across industrialized and poor nations (Baldwin, Ito, and Sato 2014). Due to discrepancies in comparative advantage in GVC participation, developed countries choose to engage in high-end and intangible production activities such as research and development, design, and brand creation during the post-manufacturing stages. The research of the effectiveness on participation in the global value chain has made considerable use of additional data derived from a number of case studies. These states' entrance to the WTO has had a direct impact on their participation in global value chains and led to improved results (Choi Byung-il, 2020). The Ministry of Investment and Foreign Trade is responsible for accelerating Uzbekistan's WTO membership. Additionally, it should be noted that numerous organizations provide technical aid. Included are the United Nations Development Program, the Asian Development Bank, the World Bank, the United States Agency for International Development, the German Society for International Cooperation, and the Korean International Cooperation Agency (KOICA).

This research aims to provide insights into the possible paths and challenges that Uzbekistan may face on its road towards greater economic integration and growth by looking at the experiences of other nations that have joined the WTO and analyzing the country's particular economic environment.

Data source: The data provided in this research covers a period of 22 years from 2001 to 2022, and the data was collected from World Bank Database

Figure 1. Correlation between log value of GDP per capita and WTO membership

Source: Done in Stata based on data from the World Bank

It may be observed the relationship between GDP per capita value and WTO enrollment by looking at the scatter plot in Figure 1. In addition, this graph was also created by taking the GDP per capita value of 90 nations and comparing it to their membership to WTO between the

years 2001 and 2022. The log value of GDP per capita and WTO dummy variable are described correspondingly on the y axis and the x axis in this graph. According to the graph, the red line is demonstrating an increasing tendency, hence, we are able to state that when a country becomes a member of the WTO, its GDP per capita value rises accordingly. The above explanation leads us to believe that there is a connection between the WTO participation and the value of the GDP per capita, and this is the conclusion that we may draw as a result.

Table I: Estimating Governance Index with time and country fixed effect models

Variables	Coefficients
Ln(Export)	0.740*** (0.008)
Ln(FDI inflow)	0.002** (0.001)
WTO	0.283*** (0.028)
R-squared	0.832
Number of observations	1,980

*Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level. ** indicates significance at the 5% level. * indicates significance at the 10% level. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses.*

Source: Done in Stata based on data from the World Bank

The explanatory variables account for more than 83 percent of the observed variation in export in the data, as indicated by the model's R squared of 0.832. When we look at the Export term, we can see that log GDP per capita is positively correlated with the log form of Export, which is consistent with what we would anticipate given that a 1% increase in Export tends to rise GDP per capita value by about 0.74 percent. Besides, FDI inflow is statistically significant at the 5% level and has a positive coefficient too. For example, a 1% increase in FDI inflow will result in a 0.001% increase in GDP per capita, which shows increasing macroeconomic stability and population welfare. Here the most important one is having membership of WTO. As it can be seen from a table that having WTO membership is statistically significant at the 1% level and has a positive coefficient. It means, if a country is a member of WTO, it causes to grow GDP per capital value about 0.283% additionally each year.

Recommendations for Uzbekistan to Achieve WTO Membership:

1. Align Trade Policies with WTO Standards
2. Enhance Legal and Institutional Frameworks
3. Engage in Bilateral and Multilateral Negotiations
4. Promote Economic Reforms and Liberalization
5. Strengthen Trade Infrastructure and Capacity Building
6. Enhance Transparency and Good Governance
7. Foster Public and Private Sector Collaboration

In conclusion, it can be said that Uzbekistan's membership in the World Trade Organization not only increases the value of exports, but also increases the purchasing power of the country's population and the creation of an environment of pure competition in industries due to the introduction of cheap and high-quality imported products is also the cause. In addition, I think that it will encourage the effective and efficient use of the resources used by the country in an environment of pure competition.

Overall, the country's economy is expected to benefit from Uzbekistan's WTO entrance as it would create new trade and investment possibilities and foster economic development.

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